

ALIGNED NICKEL NANOSTRAND IN NANOPAPER ENABLED SHAPE-MEMORY NANOCOMPOSITE FOR HIGH SPEED

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1 General Introduction

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) belong to the class of stimuli-responsive materials and have generated significant research interest. SMPs' capability of retaining a deformed, temporary shape and to recover their initial, permanent shape upon exposure to a particular stimulus [1,2]. SMPs have plenty of advantages over their well-investigated counterpart of shape memory alloys (SMAs). Inherent advantages are their low cost, light weight, easy processing, a broad range of application temperature which can be tailored from -30 to 250 °C, durability, corrosion resistance, high capacity for elastic deformation (up to 200% in most cases) and potential biocompatibility and biodegradability [3-5]. These unique characteristics enable SMPs to be used in a myriad of fields [6]. With application domain of SMPs growing explored, some major limitations of SMPs still exist and impose great challenges to their broad utilization, especial in longer recovery time due to the low thermal conductivity, inertness to electromagnetic stimuli owing to the electrical insulation of most polymeric materials.

The utilization of electricity to induce the shape-memory effect of SMP is desirable owing to controllable and effective. Extensive research have been done on conductive SMP composites by blending an amount of conductive fillers. However, this approach always requires a high loading level of conductive fillers to achieve low electrical resistivity. With a high loading level of fillers, the high viscosity of the SMP mixture will be created resulting from strong interactions between the resin and conductive filler, and further prevent an efficient transfer of the properties of the filler to the matrix. We recently have introduced nanopaper to the electrically conductive SMP nanocomposites [7,8].

However, the interface between the nanopaper and SMP composite could be damaged or even burned out during heating due to the large dissimilarity in their thermally conductive properties. Consequently, the efficiency of heat transfer from the nanopaper to the underlying SMP composite is limited. Therefore, the enhancement in the thermally conductive properties of the SMP by blending conductive carbon nanofibers (CNFs) [9]. However, the random dispersed conductive fillers slightly depressed the recovery behavior of SMP.

Fig. 1. Morphology and structure of MWCNTs in nanopaper.

Therefore, the synergistic effect of self-assembly multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) nanopaper and vertically aligned sub-micro nickel nanostrand on the SMP nanocomposite is studied in this work. The conductive nanopaper is first used to improve the electrical properties of the SMP nanocomposite, resulting in the shape recovery can be achieved by electricity. Electromagnetic nickel nanostrands are

then blended with and, vertically aligned into the SMP resin in a magnetic field, to improve the thermal conductivity. The vertically aligned nickel nanostrands will facilitate the heat transfer from the nanopaper to the underlying SMP nanocomposite to effectively accelerate the electro-active recovery behavior. The morphology and network structure of MWCNT nanopaper were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM, ZIESS Ultra-55) at 20 kV. Figure 1 is typical surface views of raw MWCNT arrays about 500 nm. There is no large particle that came from the aggregates can be found, owing to MWCNTs being well dispersed in the suspension. The image evidenced an individual MWCNT with a diameter of 10 to 20 nm, and length of 1-15 μ m. It is observed the multiscale porous structure of nanopaper, and the porous structure with average pore size of 50 to 1000 nm. Based on the SEM observation, it is found that individual nanotube gather together to form bundles (ropes). They are mostly arranged in ropes or bundles with close-packed stacking. And a network structure is formed by molecular interaction and mechanical interlocking among nanotubes. Such a continuous network will act as a conductive path for electrons, making the nanopaper and its enabled nanocomposite electrically conductive. Figure 2 shows the nickel nanostrands were vertically aligned in the SMP resin by a magnetic field. At the same time, the morphology and structure of aligned in the SMP resin at the scale of 10 μ m is presented in the Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Nickel nanostrands are aligned in a magnetic field.

Fig. 3. Morphology and structure of aligned nickel nanostrands in aSMP resin .

2 Experimental

The MWCNTs (L-MWNT-1020) were received in powder from Shenzhen Nanometer Gang Co., Ltd, China. The nanotubes are synthesized by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and have a purity of 95%. The nanotube has an out diameter of 10 to 20 nm and 1-15 μ m in length. The non-ionic surfactant (Triton X-100, $C_{14}H_{22}O(C_2H_4O)_n$), has a hydrophilic polyethylene oxide group and a hydrophobic group. The Triton X-100 has 9.5 ethylene oxide units on average. The hydrophobic group of surfactant backbone is close contact with the MWCNTs, resulting in the modified MWCNTs having a hydrophilic polyethylene oxide group. Therefore, this non-ionic surfactant will improve the dispersion of MWCNT in aqueous solution. The MWCNT suspension was sonicated with a high-intensity sonicator (MISONIX Sonicator 4000, Qsonica, LLC, Newtown, Connecticut, USA) at room temperature for 30 min. The MWCNT suspension was sonicated with a high-intensity sonicator with ultrasound power level of 420W. Two duty cycles were used for the dispersion of the MWCNT. After the initial 15 min sonication, both MWCNT suspension and probe were cooled back to room temperature. The sonication was carried out again for another 15 min under the same condition. The MWCNT suspension was then membrane filtrated under a positive pressure to yield uniform nanopapers. After the filtration, the MWCNT nanopaper was dried in a heating oven at 120 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 h to further remove the remaining water and surfactant. Nanopapers with

performed tube networks have a macroscale dimension and can be handled as conventional fiber mats to attain controllable reinforcement dispersion and volume content.

The nickel nanostrands are supplied from Conductive Composites Company LLC, Midway, Utah, U.S. This nanostrand is grown from the Low Temperature Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Vapor Decomposition process (LTAPCVD). These Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) coated products yield a highly uniform, smooth, conformal, and ductile coating with controlled thickness between 20 and 2000 nanometers. The strands initially grow as a three dimensional self supporting lattice of interconnected filaments. The as-grown lattice is about 99.8% porous. Nanostrands are self assembled three dimensionally branched and interconnected high aspect ratio sub-micro chains of neat nickel. They form a volumetrically continuous network of nano and micro level faraday cages. As is known, the nanostrands do not take much energy to disperse them into most resins due to the strands being apart, and reduce them to particulate powder. Low shear and low viscosity methods have shown the most success for dispersing nanostrands. In this study, the as-received nanostrands are dispersed into the distilled water (with proper ratio of 1 g : 100 ml) and heated to 150°C at a rate of 10°C/min, until the water was volatilized completely. This treatment will help the as-received nanostrands to reach its nano size.

The SMP (Veriflex VF 62, supplied from Cornerstone Research Group, Inc., Dayton, Ohio, USA) is styrene-based matrix. As-received Veriflex VF 62 is a fully formable thermoset SMP resin system. And it is polymerized with the dibenzoyl peroxide hardener at a fixed weight ratio of 24:1. The resin is engineered with a glass transition temperature (T_g) of 62 °C. Cured Veriflex VF 62 has unique shape memory effect. When heated above its activation temperature (T_g), Veriflex VF 62 changes from a rigid plastic to an elastic rubber. The as treated nickel nanostrands were blended into the SMP mixture with different weight fractions (2 wt.%, 4 wt.%, 6 wt.%, and 8 wt.%, respectively). The resulting mixture was degasified in a vacuum oven to completely remove air bubbles. In this work, resin transfer molding technique was used to make the SMP nanocomposite. The nanopaper containing MWCNTs of 2.4 g was placed on the bottom of the

metallic mold. The SMP mixture was then injected into the mold. The relative pressure of the resin transfer molding was kept constant around 6 bar. After the mold filling, the mixture was cured with a ramp of approximately 1 °C/min from room temperature to 75 °C. The mold was then held at 75 °C for 3 h before being ramped to 90 °C at 15 °C/180 min. Finally, it was ramped to 110 °C at 20 °C/120 min to produce the final nanocomposites. Simultaneously, two magnets were placed in a way. After curing, a SMP nanocomposite with vertical aligned nickel nanostrands was obtained. This group of samples is named vertically aligned samples hereinafter. Another group of SMP nanocomposites was prepared in the same way but without applying the magnetic field. Hence, nickel nanostrands were randomly distributed within the SMP matrix. This group is named randomly dispersed sample hereinafter.

3 Electrically triggered shape recovery demonstration and effectiveness

The synergistic effect of nanopaper and vertical aligned nickel nanostrands on the actuation of the SMP nanocomposites were experimentally studied by using a “Π” shaped geometry and a DC power supply. The flat (permanent shape) nanocomposite specimen with a dimension of 96 mm × 4 mm × 3 mm was bent as “U”-like shape (temporary shape) at 110 °C. This temporary shape was kept until the specimen was cooled down to room temperature. A constant 20 V DC voltage was applied on the SMP nanocomposite. The shape recovery was recorded with a video camera. It can be seen that the SMP nanocomposite specimen took 90 s to complete the shape recovery. Finally, the nanocomposite specimen showed an approximately 100% recovery ratio. This fact can be attributed to the vertically aligned nickel nanostrands. These vertically aligned nickel nanostrands uniformly transfer the electrically resistive heating from nanopaper to underlying SMP part along the vertical direction, resulting in the heat transfer and dispersion significantly improved. Therefore, there is little negative effect of nanostrands on the shape recovery behavior of SMP nanocomposite in comparison with these filled with randomly dispersed fillers.

The electrically responsive behavior of SMP nanocomposite samples blended with 8 wt.% nickel nanostrands in the SMP resin has been compared.

When nickel nanostrands being aligned, the nanocomposite has a 90 s response time to the electrical stimulus. Furthermore, there is little loss in recovery ratio after the cyclic recovery being repeated up to 5 times. However, as nickel nanostrands being random, the nanocomposite has a 124 to 136 s response time under the same electric current. The loss in recovery ratio goes from bad to worse after the cyclic recovery being repeated up to 5 times. Therefore, the positive role of aligned nickel nanostrands in SMP resin is presented, i.e. fast electrically responsive behavior and approximately 100% recovery ratio.

4 Conclusions

A series of experiments were conducted to study the synergistic effect of MWCNT nanopaper and vertical aligned nickel nanostrands on the SMP nanocomposites. The actuation of the SMP nanocomposites was achieved by electrically resistive heating. The thermal and electrical properties of the styrene-based SMP resin were improved by incorporating with electrical MWCNT nanopaper and electromagnetic nickel nanostrands. These blended vertically aligned nickel nanostrands also significantly optimized the heat transfer to make the SMP nanocomposite have a perfect shape-memory effect in presence of electrical response. With four years pursuing, this exciting material is one of the goals for the study on electrically responsive SMP composites. Smart devices utilizing this exciting material are currently being designed in our lab. We envision great potential of this material in applications encompassing actuators, sensors, deployable devices and morphing structure, with convenient control by electricity.

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